

GINNNGER

From Barriers to Action

Policy Insights for Advancing Urban
Regeneration in **France**

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About GINNGER

The GINNGER project aims to create new, inclusive and participatory processes for **neighbourhood regeneration**. A **methodology** to support collaborative **decision-making** is at the project's core. GINNGER is also designing and implementing regeneration plans across six pilot sites in Europe. Four key areas of regeneration are involved: energy efficiency, renovation of buildings and urban spaces, efficient use of resources and sustainable mobility.

**GINNGER | Co-designing
neighbourhood regeneration**

The French policy context

Sustainable and inclusive **neighbourhood regeneration** is shaped by various European hard- and soft-law instruments. However, translating these EU objectives into practice often faces **fragmented competencies** across governance levels, limited integration of **participatory processes** in planning and limited **administrative capacity** at the municipal level.

French legislation on this topic includes:

- Energy and Climate Law (2019).¹
- RE2020 Building Regulation.²
- Urban Planning Code (Code de l'Urbanisme).³

Barriers, Opportunities and Recommendations

	Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budgetary constraints for municipalities, instability and frequent changes in public subsidy schemes that reduce visibility and discourage long-term investment decisions • Limited legal provisions for citizen-led urban regeneration • Lengthy administrative processing and approval times for renovation grants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex procedures for neighbourhood-level energy projects • Confusion between Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) assessments at the housing unit and at the building levels • Heritage constraints, particularly on roofs and listed architectural features, limiting the scope and methods of renovation works
	Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National decarbonisation targets aligned with EU Green Deal. • Local experimentation frameworks under “Contrats de Transition Écologique”. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy-efficiency renovations encouraged thanks to the law prohibiting the rental of poorly rated properties (based on the EPC). • Support from local energy agencies providing guidance on administrative procedures as well as free and neutral technical advice for renovation projects.
	Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase funding, legal and technical support for municipalities’ renovation plans, as well as for citizens-led energy efficiency initiatives. • Strengthen the coherence between individual and collective Energy Performance Certificate assessments to foster a global renovation strategy for entire buildings rather than isolated units. • Maintain and reinforce measures restricting the rental of inefficient properties but complement them with incentives and governance tools to engage co-ownerships in ambitious renovation plans. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid regulatory backtracking that undermines progress and market stability; instead, aim for a clear, long-term framework that supports both landlords and co-owners in meeting energy efficiency targets. • Simplify procedures for neighbourhood-level projects and support citizen-led urban regeneration initiatives. • Address the limitations to renovation of heritage-buildings, harnessing existing studies and cases that deal with the energy-efficient upgrade of historic buildings.

Conclusions and next steps

The recommendations presented are **based on GIUNGER's pilots of Paris's experience**. They aim to support authorities and policymakers to facilitating and standardising neighbourhood renovation and collaborative decision-making at the national and local level. During the next months, the project partners will expand this analysis, identifying **best practices and potential areas for harmonisation** in all pilot sites and in all four key areas of regeneration (energy efficiency, renovation of buildings and urban spaces, efficient use of resources, and sustainable mobility).

Methodology

The analysis presented was based on data collected through the assessment of policy and regulatory drivers and barriers (conducted under GIUNGER's Task 2.4), and through questionnaires circulated among pilot partners.

Sources and further information

¹ [LOI n° 2019-1147 du 8 novembre 2019 relative à l'énergie et au climat \(1\) - Légifrance](#)

² [Réglementation environnementale RE2020 | Ministères Aménagement du territoire Transition écologique](#)

³ [Code de l'urbanisme - Légifrance](#)

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